

MOTIF MEASUREMENT OF ACHIEVEMENT USING INSTRUMENT PROJECTIVE TEST IN HIGHER EDUCATION XY JAKARTA

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ABSTRACT

Students as an integral part of society is the responsibility of Higher Education as a coach to make their students have high achievement during college. especially students in XY University of Jakarta should be able to achieve a brilliant achievement that will be able to contribute scholarship to the community in general and society Automotive industry in particular. Indication of these achievements can be seen and observed through the motives contained in him as a social creature primarily motive achievement. So far, it is not yet known how far the achievement motive is in the students of XY Jakarta High School. Through this research got the achievement motive level for first semester students of XY Jakarta Higher Education. The results showed that the average student in XY Jakarta High School has low achievement motif with score / score of 0.74 needs achievement or need for achievement, abbreviated as NAch. This achievement motif can be enhanced by achievement motivation training developed by David C. Mc. Clelland. And has been applied in various developing countries.

Keywords: social motives, achievement motives

I. INTRODUCTION

XY Higher Education Jakarta is an Educational Institution under the Ministry of Industry of RI which has the vision and mission of making the advanced educational institutions supported by students who are knowledgeable and achievement, and able to create morning jobs for the graduates. Therefore, its existence needs to be supported consistently and really in order to compete with other similar universities. One of the most important factors is that the students have good quality of the students who have high achievement motives.

Please note that until now has never held research on social motives, especially achievement motives for students; whether the students have high, moderate or low achievement motives. In terms of students who have high achievement motives will greatly provide a positive value for the college where he is in college and will have an influence on the image of Higher Education itself. If you want to realize the image of the intended university, then XY Jakarta Higher Education must have a strong commitment to guide the students to be able to have high achievement motif or minimal medium. To lift the good name / image of XY Jakarta Higher Education must be supported by the quality of students with high achievement.

Supported by students who have high achievement motives, it is probable that the vision and mission of XY Jakarta Higher Education can be realized and able to elevate the degree and good name / image of XY Jakarta Higher Education in particular and the Ministry of Industry in general. To find out the high motives of the students of XY Jakarta High School will be used Projective Test instrument Thematic Apperception Test (TAT) created by Henry Murray and then developed by D. C. Clelland Clinic, from Harvard University, USA.

The purpose of this study is to find out how high the level of student achievement of XY Jakarta College, so that the result can be input and consider XY Jakarta Higher Education in taking policy for student progress in particular and of course progress, and image of XY Jakarta Higher Education in general.

2. THEORETICAL BASIS

According to Murray (1938), cited Sri Mulyani (1984), in his dissertation on Social Motives, that the determinant of behavior is necessity or "need". While Mc Clelland uses the term motive sometimes motivation in a synonymous sense, and to find the underlying motive of a behavior, the best way is to analyze the motives that exist in one's fantasies. And in his opinion all the motives derived from the learning. (Mc Clelland, 1967, in Sri Mulyani, 1984).

The conclusion of Sri Mulyani (1984), is that the motive is a potential and latent need, formed by experiences that can be relatively survive, although the possibility of change still exists, and functions to move and direct behavior to a particular destination. While motivation is a state that arises within the subject (individual-pen.) Due to the interaction between the motives and observed aspects of the situation, which are relevant to the motive and activate the behavior. While the social motive is the motive underlying the activities of the individual in his reaction to others. (Berkowiz, 1969, in Sri Mulyani, 1984). Including social motives, among others, are the motives of achievement, the motive of affiliation, and the motive of power.

Experts agree that the characteristics of people who have high achievement motives include:

1. Prefer moderate risk than high risk
2. Oriented forward and dynamic
3. There is a strong, tenacious and resilient drive to work on and accomplish a task that has certain difficulties
4. Have confidence in dealing with tasks related to achievement
5. Do not like to waste time
6. Learn a lot from self-experience and others
7. Responsible personally.

This journal only examines the achievement motives; friendly motives and motives in power are not discussed.

3. RESEARCH DATA

The data to be analyzed comes from the results of the test in the form of imaginary / imaginary stories that have been poured in writing after the respondent is given the opportunity to see the image for 10-15 seconds, then asked to write the story within 5 minutes of each picture, after finished writing the story 1, then switch to story 2 and so on until the 6th story finishes, based on the image you've seen. Observation of images and Writing stories carried out one by one to finish as many as 6 images. Thus will be collected 30 (people) x 6 = 180 imaginary stories that will be scored by TAT scoring method.

4. RESEARCH METHODS

This study aims to determine the high level of student achievement motivation in the first semester of , XY Jakarta Higher Education by taking a sample of 30 people. Implemented in the College Campus XY Jakarta, using Projective Test or Thematic Apperception Test (TAT) that is 6 different images one with the other.

To find out how high the achievement of individual motive in this case student, used what often used by Morgan, Murray and Mc Clelland that is Thematic Apperception Test (TAT). The TAT initially consisted of 19 images, then adjusted to 6 images, and Mc Clelland used these 6 images in each of his studies.

Sample image of TAT

To determine a story in a score / judged whether the story is worth the achievement motive or not can be seen from the content of the existing narrative as follows:

1. When in the story there is an attempt to achieve success both with an indication of exceeding the size of self that has been achieved or exceed the standard of another (standard of excellent).
2. If in the story there is a hard work effort, diligent, tireless, new invention / innovation (unique accomplishment).
3. If in the story there is business involvement in long term involvement.

The story scored achievement motif is called Achievement Imagery (AI), while the story that got the score is not the achievement motion there are 2 titles namely Task Imagery (TI) or the stories about routine task, no performance achievement and Unrelated Imagery (UI) or stories that are not related to job duties.

Even Mc Clelland concluded that achievement motives can be trained through an intensive training package under the name Achievement Motivation Training (AMT). Until now the training is still being conducted in various state enterprises (SOEs), BUMS, education, SMEs and the general public with various variations of adjustments with specific goals and interests. In this context, the author only focuses on the measurement of achievement motif by using the Projective Test instrument, TAT scoring method which is often used by Mc Clelland

in conducting research, including when conducting demonstration in Indonesia in 1972 through UNIDO project in cooperation with RI; in this case the Ministry of Industry, Ministry of Manpower, Universities ITB, UI and PT. Loud noise.

5. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. ASSESSMENT BASED ON THE MAIN CATEGORY

From the data (story imaginary) that there are 30 respondents, each respondent 6 stories so that there are a total of 180 stories. Once in the value generates as table 1 below:

Table 1. Major Category Scoring Results

Respondents	Achievement Story	From Number of Stories	Respondents	Achievement Story	From Number of Stories
1	2	6	16	2	6
2	0	6	17	2	6
3	3	6	18	1	6
4	1	6	19	3	6
5	1	6	20	2	6
6	2	6	21	2	6
7	3	6	22	0	6
8	0	6	23	0	6
9	0	6	24	1	6
10	2	6	25	1	6
11	2	6	26	2	6
12	4	6	27	1	6
13	0	6	28	2	6
14	1	6	29	1	6
15	3	6	30	0	6

2. ASSESSMENT BASED ON SUB CATEGORIES

From the results of the main category assessment, each story achievement traced elements as follows:

- a. elements that indicate the need (need) is abbreviated as N.
- b. elements that indicate activity (activity) abbreviated Act.
- c. the element that shows the shadow of success (success anticipation) abbreviated Sa.
- d. elements that show failure anticipation (abbreviated Fa).
- e. elements that indicate the existence of barriers / constraints in the self (personal block) abbreviated Bp.
- f. elements that indicate the existence of obstacles / constraints from outside the self / outside world (world block) abbreviated Bw.
- g. unsusers indicate the existence of an effort to ask for help from other parties H
- h. elements that show a sense of fun / happy / proud / satisfied for the results achieved (positive feeling) abbreviated F +.
- i. elements that show a sense of disappointment / sad / upset over the results achieved a failure (negative feeling) abbreviated F-
- j. Is the written story focused on a prestatative purpose (theme) abbreviated as Th.

If in one story achievement contains all the elements - the above elements then the story is considered perfect with a total value of 11 needs / achievement motif or as popular 11 N.ach (need for achievement). The details are as follows:

- | | |
|--|-----------------------|
| 1. Story achievement (AI) score: 1 N.ach | 7. Bw score: 1N ach |
| 2. N score: 1N.ach | 8. H score: 1 N ach |
| 3. Act score: 1 N.ach | 9. F + score: 1 N ach |
| 4. Sa score: 1 N.ach | 10. F- score: 1 N ach |
| 5. Fa score: 1 N.ach | 11.Th score: 1 N ach |
| 6. Bp score: 1 N.ach | |

If the story of the entire story (180 stories) of the achievement story and each story of achievement contains the elements mentioned above, then the result is:

$$180 \times 11 \text{ N- ach} = 198 \text{ N.ach}$$

Based on sub-category scoring, results are obtained as Table 2. The following:

Table 2. Results of subcategory scores

Respondents	Main category scores & Sub Category	From Number of Stories	Respondents	Main category scores & Sub Category	From Number of Stories
1	7	6	16	8	6
2	-3	6	17	7	6
3	13	6	18	3	6
4	4	6	19	20	6
5	1	6	20	5	6
6	6	6	21	7	6
7	11	6	22	-5	6
8	-5	6	23	-4	6
9	-3	6	24	5	6
10	8	6	25	2	6
11	5	6	26	6	6
12	15	6	27	3	6
13	0	6	28	7	6
14	0	6	29	1	6
15	10	6	30	0	6

Total calculations of the main categories and sub categories are: 134 N.ach in 180 stories (already taken into account from the reduction of unrelated story of Imagery)

So the average per person / student of XY Jakarta Higher Education semester 1 has achievement level $134/180 = 0,74$ N.ach.

Under the terms, the standard achievement motives are as follows:

Score: -1 to 2 N.ach is categorized as low, 2. Score: 3 to 6 N. ach is categorized as being, 3. Score: 7 to 11 N.ach is categorized high

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. CONCLUSION

a. From the result of scoring by using Projective Test instrument or Thematic Apperception Test (TAT), the Student Achievement Motive 1st semester of XY Jakarta Higher Education has average grade achievement 0,74 N.ach which means low achievement motif.

b. When viewed individually, then there are 6 (six) respondents whose scores (both the results of major categories or sub categories) have not shown the achievement motive, or in other words still get a score of zero (0) or negative score means that his thoughts are still fixed to the purpose of task unassistable and / or Affiliative routine tasks that lead to friendship, but according to Mc Clelland can still be developed through exercises, one of them is Outstanding Motivation Training. While there are 1 (one) respondents who have a moderate achievement motif with a score of 3.33 N.ach

SUGGESTION

a. According to Mc Clelland this achievement motif can be developed through intensive training that is Achievement Motivation Training. Therefore, to encourage students to have higher achievement motives and in turn will be able to produce out put according to the expectations of Higher Education of XY Jakarta and of course the students themselves, the Achievement Motivation Training for XY Jakarta Higher Education students is considered to be very urgent.

b. As an effort to realize the Achievement Motivation Training in XY Jakarta Higher Education, it should be conducted on a regular basis which is timed to be adjusted by lecturing scheduling or academic calendar.

c. The achievement of this achievement motivation training is entirely the authority of the Higher Education Leadership of XY Jakarta, but it should be given to the students of semester 1 or the final semester with the consideration if held for the first semester students, the students will be able to quickly adjust to the vision and mission of XY Jakarta Higher Education. Meanwhile, when the training is given to the students of the final semester, it will provide direction and as a provision to enter the world of work.

d. Realizing this journal is very simple, then the future may be continued to other researchers which is more scientific in terms of researching with particular variable variables, for the sake of interest Higher Education XY Jakarta as a whole; eg "The Relationship between Achievement Motive with Fast Graduation Student ", or " Relationship Motives Achievement of Self Confidence College student".

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